

9th Annual Spring Scientific Symposium in Anesthesiology and Intensive Care

April 12th – April 14th 2019
Niš, Serbia

PROCEEDING

10th
ANNIVERSARY

European
Society of
Anaesthesiology

ESA

WFSA
WORLD FEDERATION OF SOCIETIES OF
ANAESTHESIOLOGISTS

NINTH ANNUAL SPRING
SCIENTIFIC SYMPOSIUM
IN ANESTHESIOLOGY
AND INTENSIVE CARE

PROCEEDING

SCIENTIFIC SYMPOSIUM

April 12-14, 2019

Niš, Serbia

**NINTH ANNUAL SPRING SCIENTIFIC SYMPOSIUM
IN ANESTHESIOLOGY AND INTENSIVE CARE**

PROCEEDING

Scientific symposium

April 12-14, 2019

Niš, Serbia

Editorial board

Assoc. Prof. Radmilo Janković, Ph.D.

Assoc. Prof. Biljana Stošić, Ph.D.

Assist. Prof. Ivana Budić, Ph.D.

Tijana Maričić Grbeša, MD

Publisher

"Galaksijanis", Niš

For the publisher

Mlađan Ranđelović, manager

Technical editor

Mile Ž. Ranđelović

Printed by

"Galaksijanis", Niš

2019.

Curculation

500

ISBN 978-86-6233-230-1

CIP - Каталогизacija y publikaciji –
Народна библиотека Србије, Београд

616-089.5(082)
615.211/.216(082)

ANNUAL Spring Scientific Symposium in Anesthesiology and Intensive
Care (9 ; 2019 ; Niš)

Proceeding / Ninth Annual Spring Scientific Symposium in
Anesthesiology and Intensive Care, April 12-14, 2019, Niš, Serbia ;
[editorial board Radmilo Janković ... [et al.]]. - Niš : Galaksijanis, 2019
(Niš : Galaksijanis). - 147 str. : ilustr. ; 29 cm

Tiraž 500. - Bibliografija uz svaki rad.

ISBN 978-86-6233-230-1

a) Анестезиологија - Зборници
COBISS.SR-ID 275719948

MECHANICAL VENTILATION IN CHILDREN

Anna Uram-Benka^{1,2}, Izabella Fabri Galambos^{1,2}, Goran Rakić^{1,2}, Marina Pandurov^{1,2}

¹Medical Faculty, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

²Institute for the Healthcare of Children and Youth of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

Mechanical ventilation refers to the use of life-support technology to perform the work of breathing for patients who are unable to breathe on their own.

The overall aim of mechanical ventilation is to relieve the distress of dyspnea, reduce the work of breathing, improve oxygenation, and improve CO₂ clearance in order to improve gas exchange.

The art of mechanical ventilation witnessed a revolution during the last three decades for improving the ways to protect the lung from injury as a result of positive pressure. The care for ventilated pediatric patients requires an extensive understanding of respiratory mechanics and pathophysiology of cardiopulmonary diseases. Many of the fundamental principles of respiratory physiology and gas exchange are similar to those of adults, but there are many differences in the anatomy, physiology and pathology with these two populations.

As the adage says, 'children are not small adults', the management of ventilated pediatric patients requires an appreciation of the susceptibility of their lung tissue to developing an injury, congenital anomalies, disease processes specific to pediatric population, and the potential equipment-related difficulties associated with small patients. Each pediatric patient who requires mechanical ventilation represents a unique clinical problem. Regarding the condition of the child's lungs there are different modes of setting a mechanical ventilator that can differ from the standard of adults to better co-operate with the child's respiratory functions. Children in general need frequent therapeutic actions from the health care staff as they are more liable to complications regarding their incomplete or immature systems.

Mechanical ventilation can be lifesaving, but more than 50% of complications in conditions that require intensive care are related to ventilatory support, particularly if it is prolonged. Mechanical ventilation with positive pressure is a technique that has been employed in pediatric intensive care units (PICUs) with increasing frequency. The percentage of mechanical ventilation varies from 30 to 64% in PICUs. Since its introduction into the modern PICUs, mechanical ventilation has undergone continuous evolution. There has been an explosion of new ventilator modes, many of which have been incorporated into routine clinical practice without evidence of their efficacy or their superiority over other modes of ventilation. Currently, pressure modes are generally used for children.

The indications for mechanical ventilation are respiratory failure (pneumonia, bronchiolitis, lung hemorrhage, muscle disease, laryngotracheobronchiolitis), cardiovascular failure together with hypotension (heart

failure, myocarditis, spell attack), septic shock, central nervous system disease (meningitis, encephalitis, coma, bleeding, tumor), and safety airway, especially in critical situations like sepsis.

Airway and tracheal tube

While the majority of tracheal tubes placed in critically ill children are for the purposes of facilitating mechanical ventilation, decisions at the time of airway placement may have important implications. Features specific to pediatric patients (e.g. size, anatomy) leave them at particular risk for compromising the security of their airway.

Uncuffed tubes have traditionally been used in children due to historic anatomical surveys revealing the conical shape of the airway during the first several years of life. However, due to the common occurrence of ineffective ventilation and the egress of inhalatory anaesthetics in the presence of a large air leak, cuffed tubes in pediatrics have grown in popularity. Early investigations showed that tubes with high-pressure, low-volume cuffs had similar rates of post-extubation stridor when compared to uncuffed tubes. Despite this information, the choice of tube type in young children remains controversial, as long-term data on airway injury are lacking. Currently, the use of cuffed or uncuffed tubes is considered an acceptable standard of practice. If cuffed TTs are used, cuff pressure should be routinely monitored and kept below 20 cmH₂O. Uncuffed TTs should be sized to allow a leak of ~ 20cmH₂O.

Breathing and Oxygenation

The majority of intubations in the pediatric intensive care unit are performed to facilitate oxygenation, clearance of carbon dioxide (CO₂), decrease the work of breathing, or a combination of these clinical issues. Hypoxemia in ventilated patients is treated in several ways: increasing the fraction of inspired O₂ to increase the partial pressure of oxygen in the alveoli, optimizing alveolar patency via recruitment manoeuvres, and providing adequate PEEP to maintain functional residual capacity (FRC).

The main clinical target involved in regulating CO₂ clearance is alveolar ventilation (minute ventilation, less dead space ventilation). A patient's PaCO₂ is directly proportional to CO₂ production by the body, and inversely proportional to CO₂ clearance by alveolar ventilation. Permissive hypercapnia continues to be used regularly

in ventilated pediatric patients in the ICU. Typical strategies aim for a gradual increase in PaCO₂ to < 8–10 kPa and allow for a corresponding mild acidosis (e.g. pH 7.25–7.33). This permits patients to be ventilated with lower plateau pressures and tidal volumes in an effort to reduce ventilator-induced lung injury.

Modes of mechanical ventilation

Multiple mechanical ventilation modes are currently used in clinical practice to provide respiratory support for a wide spectrum of patients, ranging from no lung disease to acute lung injury (ALI) and ARDS. To date no data exist to determine the ventilatory mode that provides the greatest benefit with the least risk to an individual pediatric patient. Each new generation of conventional mechanical ventilators brings new ventilation modes and new features. However, despite a multitude of new modes, no study has shown that any mode is better than others in improving survival rates for ALI patients. It should be noted that in reality it might not be possible to demonstrate a significant change in mortality based only on changes in ventilator modes, because of the extremely low baseline mortality rate for intubated infants and children in pediatric ICUs.

Mandatory ventilation

In this mode of ventilation, all breaths are triggered, limited and cycled by the ventilator.

Volume control - in this mode the machine gives a constant volume every breath (tidal volume), during a set inspiratory time with a set frequency and constant inspiratory flow. The ventilator controls all timing parameters of the breath.

Pressure control ventilation - in this mode the ventilator delivers positive pressure up to a predetermined pressure limit above PEEP during a selected inspiratory time and at a set frequency.

Pressure Regulated Volume Control (PRVC) - a control mode which delivers a set tidal volume with each breath at the lowest possible peak pressure. It delivers a breath with a decelerating flow pattern that is thought to be less harmful to the lung.

Inverse Ratio Ventilation - pressure control mode in which inspiration time is longer than the expiration time ($I : E > 1$). Mean airway pressure can be increased without increasing peak inspiratory pressure in order to improve oxygenation but limit the possibility of barotrauma. There is a high risk for air trapping. The patient should be deeply sedated and may also be paralyzed as well.

Assisted ventilation

This is essentially identical to the respective controlled modes of ventilation except that the patient's inspiratory efforts trigger the ventilator to deliver assisted breaths using the preselected limit and cycle variables. Assisted ventilation can be provided with either pressure or flow as the limit variable.

Intermittent mandatory ventilation – allows spontaneous breathing between positive pressure breaths with

a preset inspiratory time and frequency. The positive pressure breaths may be either pressure or volume limited.

Airway pressure release ventilation (APRV) – provides a continuous gas flow circuit to vary the airway pressure between two different CPAP levels. Airway pressures are decreased or „released“ intermittently from the preset CPAP to a lower or ambient pressure. Lung volume transiently decreases, allowing gas to exit the lungs passively, thereby augmenting alveolar ventilation.

Mandatory minute ventilation – this mode allows mandatory delivery of a predetermined minute volume that is distributed variably between spontaneous and mechanical breaths and depends on the patient's spontaneous ventilation.

Supported ventilation – is defined as a breath triggered by the patient, limited by the ventilator, and cycled by the patient. Ventilation is spontaneous and the patient initiates and terminates each breath and is only used in patients with adequate ventilatory drives (continuous positive airway pressure, pressure support ventilation, volume support ventilation).

High Frequency ventilation

Because of its potential to reduce volutrauma, there has been a surge of interest in high-frequency ventilation in the past few years. High-frequency ventilation may improve blood gases values because, in addition to the gas transport by convection, other mechanisms of gas exchange may become active at high frequencies. There has been extensive clinical use of various high-frequency ventilators in neonates. Small randomized trials suggest that bronchopulmonary dysplasia may be prevented with high-frequency jet ventilation, but results are inconclusive. The largest randomized trial of high-frequency ventilation revealed that early use of high-frequency oscillatory ventilation did not improve outcome. Although various randomized controlled trials show heterogeneous results, meta-analyses largely confirm the original findings. However, there are trends toward decreases in bronchopulmonary dysplasia/chronic lung disease, but increases in severe intraventricular hemorrhage and periventricular leukomalacia as well as small increases in air leaks with high-frequency oscillatory ventilation or high-frequency flow interrupters. High-frequency ventilation is a safe alternative for infants who fail CMV.

Neurally adjusted ventilator assist

It is novel technique in pediatric ventilation. The theory underpinning NAVA is that the most physiological means of determining the need for minute ventilation arises from the patient's own respiratory centre. NAVA uses an oesophageal catheter to measure diaphragmatic electrical activity and uses this information to direct ventilation. It is suspected that coordinating the timing of ventilator breaths based on diaphragmatic electrical activity is superior to current techniques based on sensing changes in circuit gas flow, as there is less of a delay. Diaphragmatic electrical activity also permits some estimation of the magnitude of ventilator breath to deliver. The combination of these features is thought to result in improved patient–ventilator synchrony and may po-

tentially benefit those with neuromuscular conditions in particular.

Despite the promising theoretical advantages of NAVA, more experience and study is needed. Oesophageal catheters designed to monitor diaphragmatic activity are costly and their appropriate positioning can be difficult. In addition, it is unknown whether the intact respiratory centre can appropriately regulate ventilation during critical illness.

Weaning from invasive mechanical ventilation

In children, limited guidance exists regarding weaning and extubation. Two reasons are the short duration of MV and low extubation failure rates (2–20%). Various weaning concepts, including spontaneous breathing trials and closed-loop weaning, have failed to show superiority over clinical judgment. Yet, no single or combination of variables, including respiratory mechanics, gas exchange and patient ability to maintain work of breathing, reliably predicts weaning success.

Complication

Attaching a patient to a mechanical ventilator in intensive care unit is considered a life-saving procedure because of its ability to assist life continuation by helping the patient to carry out his respiratory activity in oxygenation and CO₂ clearance. It is also highly risky for making these patients susceptible to various complications. Mechanical ventilation can result in important complications including pneumothorax, atelectasis, ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP), barotrauma, volutrauma, obstruction of the tracheal tube during the intubation period, tracheal edema and tracheal stenosis after the extubation period. In this respect, a patient treated with mechanical ventilation must be followed by the pediatric intensive team and in a PICU.

Conclusion

Mechanical ventilation is the most important measure of respiratory support in intensive care units. Knowledge the specifics in childhood, the choice of an adequate mode of mechanical ventilation and optimizing patient-ventilator interaction are essential to minimizing adverse events. Besides the classic forms underlined the are newer forms od ventilators available which have made major contributions to improving the quality of mechanical ventilation in children.

The practice of pediatric MV is predominantly based on anecdotal experiences, institutional belief and, to a certain degree, extrapolation of adult-based data. This is clearly an unwanted situation for such a commonly practised intervention in the pediatric critical care environment. The most important issue affecting the field of pediatric mechanical ventilation is the need for multi-center, randomized, prospective studies.

References

1. Harless J, Ramaiah R, Bhananker SM. Pediatric airway management. *International Journal of Critical Illness and Injury Science*. 2014;4(1):65-70.
2. Gupta R, Rosen D. Paediatric mechanical ventilation in the intensive care unit. *British journal of Anaesthesia*. 2016;(16):422-26.
3. Terzi N, Piquilloud L, Rozé H, et al. Clinical review: update on neurally adjusted ventilatory assist report of a round-table conference. *Critical Care*. 2012;16:225.
4. Rimensberger P.C, Cheifetz I.M, Kneyber M.C. The top ten unknowns in paediatric mechanical ventilation. *Intensive Care Med*. 2018;44:366–370.
5. Kneyber M.C.J, de Luca D, Calderin E et al. Recommendations for mechanical ventilation of critically ill children from the Paediatric Mechanical Ventilation Consensus Conference (PEMVECC). *Intensive Care Med*. 2017;43:1764–1780.
6. Gupta M, Bergel M, Betancourt N, Mahan V.L. Neurally adjusted ventilatory assist mode in pediatric intensive care unit and pediatric cardiac care unit. *Explor Res Hypothesis Med*. 2017;(2):33–37.